

What is Tuberculosis?

Tuberculosis (TB) is a severe infectious disease caused by bacteria called mycobacteria.

How can I get TB?

People with active TB have symptoms, but not every one of them can spread mycobacteria.

TB bacteria are spread through the air, when a person with infectious TB disease is coughing, speaking or singing. People nearby can inhale/breathe in the bacteria and become infected. In the vast majority of cases, ill people spread bacteria to people they spend the most time with every day: family members, friends, co-workers or schoolmates.

Am I infected or am I ill?

It is important to know, that not everyone who is infected with TB develops the disease. Persons who are infected and do not have symptoms harbour latent TB infection (LTBI), while those with symptoms have active TB: they are ill.

Those who have LTBI, are not sick, they have no symptoms and do not spread bacteria. Most people with LTBI never develop the disease.

However, people who have a weak immune system or suffer from risk factors have a higher risk to develop TB.

Which are the risk factors for getting sick?

While some people develop active TB very soon following the infection, some might get sick years after. If you are infected with TB, and you belong to the risk factor group, you might develop the disease.

Some conditions that might cause your immune system not to work properly are:

- HIV infection
- Substance abuse
- Diabetes mellitus
- Severe kidney disease
- Low body weight
- Organ transplants
- Cancer

- Immunosuppressive medical treatment
- Being a child or an elder

Other circumstances also favour the disease:

- To be close to someone who has active TB without a mask
- To work or live with people who are at high risk to develop TB
- To suffer a big stressful event (such as being a war refugee, being homeless, etc)

If I am sick, which symptoms can I have?

TB can cause symptoms that last long (more than 2 weeks!) and can be different, depending on which part of the body bacteria is affecting. Most of the time TB will affect your lungs, but any part of your body can be affected.

Some of the symptoms you might experience are:

- Cough with sputum and blood
- Chest pain
- Weakness
- Unexplained important weight loss
- Fever and night sweats

Can TB be cured?

Yes, TB can be cured and can be prevented. Early diagnosis is the key. The early diagnosis guarantees prompt treatment, will increase your chances to recover totally and will prevent your loved ones to get infected.

Do you need more information?

There are people whose work is devoted to fighting tuberculosis. Please do not hesitate to contact the healthcare professionals at your nearest healthcare Center.

- Tuberculosis is a severe infectious disease caused by bacteria called mycobacteria.
- Tuberculosis can be cured and can be prevented.
- People can become infected by inhaling/breathing in the bacteria.
- Identifying early if you are ill, will allow you to be treated as soon as possible, will increase your chances to recover totally and will prevent your loved ones to get infected.

Illustrated by Laura Gimés and Pepón Meneses

Developed by IGTP-HUGTIP in collaboration with ASPB & SMA-TB
 Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020
 research and innovation program [GA-847762]

WHAT IS TUBERCULOSIS?

Can tuberculosis be cured?

How can I get tuberculosis?

Which symptoms can I have?

Funded by
 the European Union